

Ferromagnetic cluster spin glass nature in $\text{Sm}_3\text{Ag}_{2.55}\text{Al}_{8.45}$

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Abstract

Spin glass (SG) has become one of the main streams of research in condensed matter physics over the years [1-2]. However the real origin of this behaviour is still under debate. The compound $\text{Sm}_3\text{Ag}_{2.55}\text{Al}_{8.45}$ is reported to adopt the orthorhombic $\text{La}_3\text{Al}_{11}$ structure type. The indication for the presence of ferromagnetic SG was obtained from the anomalous behaviour in ac susceptibility besides ferromagnetic ground state in dc susceptibility. Susceptibility exhibits a slope change at $T_c = 15$ K. The irreversibility between zero field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) is highly dominant below the freezing temperature $T_f = 13.3$ K, 11 K, 9 K, 5 K for the steady fields of $H = 100$ Oe, 1 kOe, 3 kOe, 10 kOe respectively. The non- vanishing of irreversibility in magnetization for an applied field of $H = 20$ kOe, which is relatively large for FM materials suggests the presence of randomly quenched ferromagnetic clusters below $T_c = 15$ K [3, 5]. In this symposium, a detailed discussions will be presented on the structural, ac and dc magnetic susceptibility, isothermal magnetization, and heat capacity investigations on a polycrystalline $\text{Sm}_3\text{Ag}_{2.55}\text{Al}_{8.45}$ sample which exhibits ferromagnetic spin glass behaviour.

Keywords: Spin glass, ferromagnetic, heat capacity

Reference

- [1] K. Binder, and A. P. Young, Rev. Mod. Phys. 58 (1986) 801-976.
- [2] M. B. Weissman, Rev. Mod. Phys. 65 (1993) 829-839.
- [3] P A Joy, Anil Kumar and S K Date, J. Phys. Condens. Matter. 10 (1998) 11049–11054
- [4] J.A. Mydosh, Spin Glass: An Experimental Introduction, Taylor & Francis, London, 1993.